

5G Network Enhancements to Support Ambient IoT Devices

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Abstract—With the advent of 5G networks and the enablement of massive machine type communications (mMTC), a plethora of use cases envisioned in vertical sectors, being manufacturing, transportation, healthcare, power industry, and many more, has been realized. The proliferation of Internet of Things (IoT) devices has revolutionized the way these sectors operate, unleashing the possibility for new disruptive use cases and applications. As the variety of use cases dependent on sensors expands, some new requirements demand for battery-less or limited-capacity IoT devices which are harvesting energy from their environment, broadly recognized as Ambient IoT (AIoT) devices. The existing 5G network architecture is not inherently supporting AIoT devices, and some further enhancements are requested to satisfy the peculiarities such kind of devices exhibit in terms of communication. This paper proposes new functions and methods which enable the 5G network to onboard AIoT devices and support their respective use cases. More precisely, we propose a new Network Function (NF) in the 5G Core Network (CN) Service Based Architecture (SBA), dedicated for managing the communication of AIoT devices with their corresponding application servers, as well as details on the appropriate message flows to support this kind of communication. In addition, we propose novel procedures and methods, deemed necessary for securing the AIoT messages transferred end-to-end. Finally, this paper contributes to existing research in the field by envisioning the necessary network signaling messages, which will allow for translation of AIoT transmission requirements into appropriate energy-transfer actions applied by the 5G network components, in an attempt to energize such kind of devices.

Keywords—Ambient IoT; Ambient IoT Provisioning Server; Ambient IoT Function; Energy harvesting; 5G network;

I. INTRODUCTION

An Ambient IoT (AIoT) device is an Internet of Things (IoT) device powered by harvesting energy, such as Radio Frequency (RF) energy, solar energy, wind energy, vibrations, etc. An ambient IoT device is battery-less and may have limited energy storage capability (e.g., using an internal capacitor). According to [1], RF energy harvesting enables wireless IoT devices to harvest energy from RF signals available in their environment, such as RF signals transmitted from mobile networks or from nearby Wi-Fi networks. [2] mentions that RF energy harvesting is a promising technology

that enables self-sustainable wireless IoT networks and analyzes the energy harvesting performance of a Wi-Fi-based IoT network.

Research conducted in [3] mentions that research challenges need to be addressed to enable the large-scale deployment of energy harvesting solutions for IoT environments, and further research and advancements in this field may lead to new ways to enhance 5G networks for supporting RF energy harvesting in IoT devices. On the contrary, it is also possible that advances in 5G technology can provide more opportunities for RF energy harvesting in IoT devices by increasing the available RF signals in the environment, e.g., by increasing the power or the transmission rate of RF signals transmitted by a 5G network.

The work presented in [4], proposes an energy and spectrum efficient IoT network for 5G systems, where spectrum is shared with the cellular system, increasing spectrum efficiency. The proposed concept is dividing the IoT network in clusters of sensor nodes, each managed by a cluster head which is responsible to find the spectrum opportunities in the cellular band and schedule the transmission of the sensor nodes, as well as to perform energy transfer to them. The authors emphasize on the trade-off between the time spent for transmissions and the time spent for harvesting, however, it is assumed that the cluster head is a powerful device, connected to a reliable source of energy, in contrast to the specific requirements of battery-less AIoT devices we are discussing here. Similarly, sensor nodes are considered to be less powerful than the cluster head, but they are also running on small batteries with tight energy constraints.

[5] offers a complete study around the various means to enable wireless energy harvesting (WEH), indicating that it has proven to be one of the most promising solutions in terms of simplicity, ease of implementation, and availability. This article contains an overview of enabling technologies for efficient WEH, such as the RF-to-DC Rectifier, the Wake-Up Radio Scheme, and the Power Management Unit (PMU).

An overview of RF energy harvesting for 5G is presented in [8], where the authors initially analyze the 5G requirements and use cases suitable for RF energy harvesting, and then review the available energy harvesting techniques in 5G networks as well as current networks' constraints. Their survey, however, is concentrated on the physical layer and the

low-level radio aspects required to enable wireless information exchange and power transfer.

All the above-mentioned studies illustrate the extensive research performed around the various techniques AIoT devices can leverage to harvest energy from their environment and the technical aspects have been thoroughly analyzed. However, even though these studies sufficiently cover the physical-layer techniques for radio-communication and energy harvesting of AIoT devices, they lack in providing detailed procedures and methods for establishing end-to-end AIoT device communication with Application Servers (AS) over 5G networks, and in addition, how transmission-related instructions initiated by ASs can be translated into energy-related actions applied onto the AIoT devices with the assistance of the 5G network.

In this direction, standardization attempts for communication of AIoT devices with 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) networks, have just been launched. In the context of Release-19, the 3GPP Service & System Aspects working group 1 (aka SA1) has initiated a study item on “Ambient power-enabled Internet of Things”, which aims at defining the service requirements for mobile networks (5th Generation (5G) and beyond) to support communication with ambient IoT devices. The most relevant record in this field, is 3GPP’s Technical Report (TR) 22.840 v1.0.0 [6], which mainly documents use cases, traffic scenarios, AIoT device constraints, and identifies new potential 5G service requirements for ambient power-enabled Internet of Things.

However, neither in literature nor in 3GPP specifications, are considered any technical procedures for establishing end-to-end communication of AIoT devices with the 5G network. This paper identifies the gap and proposes a detailed solution to support end-to-end communication of AIoT devices with the 5G network, focusing on the 5G Core Network (CN) domain aspects and describing how decisions determined in the CN are applied in the Next Generation Radio Access Network (NG-RAN), following a holistic end-to-end approach.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section II is analyzing the components introduced in the context of our proposed solution, such as the Ambient IoT device, the Ambient IoT Provisioning Server which is expected to store various ambient IoT device information, as well as a new Network Function (NF) in the 5G CN Service Based Architecture (SBA), dedicated to assist the network in providing communication functionality to ambient IoT devices. Section III presents the end-to-end solution describing the communication patterns and message flows which enable the onboarding of AIoT devices into the 5G network, allowing them to further exploit the capabilities offered by the network. Section IV examines how the network can support the transmission requirements (Tx Requirements) of AIoT devices. Finally, section V presents the conclusion and future directions.

II. COMPONENTS’ DESCRIPTION

Trying to analyze the communication requirements of ambient IoT devices as imposed by their intrinsic characteristics, some new components have been identified as essential to facilitate those devices’ communication with the 5G network. In this section we describe these new components,

as well as some characteristics of the Ambient IoT devices which demand the presence of the new elements.

A. Ambient IoT Device

As already described in the introductory section, ambient IoT are battery-less devices which accommodate specific use cases requesting for thin, long-lasting, and environmentally friendly devices. As such, those devices have been designed to operate with substantially less power than common user equipment (UE), focusing merely on the essential tasks, which might be the collection of sensory data and the fulfilment of minimal communication requirements. The various resource limitations of AIoT devices, request for lean procedures in the way those devices communicate with the 5G network, so in contrast to user equipment (UEs), ambient IoT devices do not support a Universal Subscriber Identity Module (USIM) card nor follow the existing Protocol Data Unit (PDU) session establishment procedures over Non-Access Stratum (NAS). Instead, AIoT devices harvest energy from their environment to broadcast their message, and it is the network’s responsibility to receive and route the message towards the appropriate AIoT application server, as well as to ensure that the AIoT device will be able to harvest enough energy according to its transmission requirements (Tx Requirements).

In our proposed method, the AIoT “Tx Requirements” is a parameter indicating that the AIoT device should preferably send e.g., 5 messages per day. Since the AIoT device does not have a battery, it can transmit only after having harvested enough energy. When the 5G network determines that the AIoT device does not transmit as many times as required by the “Tx Requirements” parameter, it might increase the power emitted by the Next Generation NodeB(s) (gNB) in the vicinity of the AIoT device, in order to assist the device harvest more energy and increase its number of transmissions. The use of this parameter within our proposed solution, is further described in Section IV.

B. Ambient IoT Provisioning Server

A new component introduced to deal with the unconventional AIoT communication demands, is the Ambient IoT Provisioning Server (AIPS). AIPS might be a commodity hardware server, hosted and maintained by a 3rd party entity (i.e., in the Cloud; not necessarily owned by the Mobile Network Operator (MNO)), which is capable of storing ambient IoT device manufacturing information (i.e., manufacturing information from devices belonging to a single or multiple AIoT device vendors) and facilitates communication of AIoT devices with the 5G Core network. In addition, AIPS validates the authenticity of an AIoT device, assisting the 5G Core network operations with respect to the AIoT related validation procedures.

The ambient IoT provisioning server may expose APIs to facilitate the interaction with its counterparts. Its main role is to store various AIoT manufacturing information (i.e., the ambient IoT device identifier (DevID), the ambient IoT device Security Information (Security Info), and the ambient IoT device profile (Dev profile)) which are provided to AIPS by the Ambient IoT Device Vendor, who is in essence the manufacturer of the ambient IoT device. In response to storing the AIoT device manufacturing information, AIPS provides a token to the AIoT device vendor, which is printed on the

device along with some other device manufacturing information and is thereafter used to validate device claim request messages initiated by the owner/operator of the device (the one who bought the AIoT device from the AIoT device vendor) towards the 5G network. The device claim request message (described in detail in Section III) which is initiated by the owner of the device, indicates their will to inform the network that the AIoT device belongs to them, and any subsequent AIoT device transmitted message should be forwarded to their respective AIoT application server (AIoT AS). Consequently, besides the AIoT device vendor, AIPS is also accessible by the 5G Core network's Ambient IoT Function (AIoTF) (analyzed in Section II/C), assisting this way in the validation of the claim request message by the 5G network.

C. Ambient IoT Function

As stated earlier, also the 5G network requests for some additional enhancements in order to accommodate the ambient IoT devices. To this end, a specific network function, named Ambient IoT Function (AIoTF), is proposed to complement the existing NFs, and facilitate communication of ambient IoT devices with the 5G network. The AIoTF is expected to oversee all the procedures related to Ambient IoT communications from the 5G Core network perspective, serving as a termination point for the messages transmitted by the AIoT devices towards the respective ambient IoT application servers, which reside in the data network (DN). In addition, the AIoTF caters for as an intermediate element in the AIoT device onboarding procedure by (a) handling the AIoT device claim request messages (initiated by the AIoT owner/operator), (b) interacting with AIPS to authenticate the device claimed operator, (c) determining the proper routing of AIoT transmitted messages towards the appropriate AIoT application server, and finally (d) creating and delivering instructions to the gNB(s) on the appropriate amount of energy to be emitted in the form of RF signals, so that sufficient energy can be harvested by the AIoT devices in their vicinity, in an attempt to satisfy the AIoT devices' Tx Requirements. (An AIoT device might be required to transmit a message 5 times per day.) The AIoTF is anticipated to conform to the 5G network's SBA, allowing for smooth integration into the core network and easing interaction with other network functions, such as the Network Exposure Function (NEF), the Access and Mobility Management Function (AMF), etc.

III. AMBIENT IOT DEVICE ONBOARDING

This section describes the steps of the proposed method for onboarding an AIoT device in a 5G network. The onboarding procedure of an AIoT device (illustrated in Fig. 1) is required for appropriate configuration of the 5G network with device-specific information (also referred to as AIoT Device Context) and is essentially the one that enables the network to support end-to-end communication for this device. A key characteristic of the below method is that it enables onboarding of a device in a 5G network (i.e., makes this device operational in the 5G network) without the 5G network having subscription data for this device, in contrast to the handling of traditional mobile devices. For simplicity, the procedure below presents the steps involved in onboarding a single AIoT device. However, it is

noted that similar steps can be applied for onboarding a plurality (or a group) of AIoT devices.

As depicted in Fig. 1, in step 0, the AIoT device vendor manufactures a new AIoT device. Information stored in the AIoT device contains its own unique device identifier (DevID) and Security information, including security keys. The use of these keys is discussed further below.

In step 1a, the AIoT device vendor sends a "Device Provisioning Request" message towards an AIoT Provisioning Server (AIPS). This message is sent for securely storing device-relevant information in the AIPS. It is assumed (a) that the AIPS is equipped with a highly secured storage medium, in which the device-relevant information is stored and (b) that all messages to and from the AIPS are confidentiality and integrity protected with means already available in literature and the information security sector. The "Device Provisioning Request" message contains the "DevID", the "Security Info" and the device profile ("Dev profile") of the AIoT device. The "Dev profile" of the AIoT device includes device characteristics, i.e., if the device is designed to only transmit (Tx-only), if the device is capable of transmitting and receiving (Tx-Rx), the energy harvesting capabilities of the device, etc.

In step 1b, AIPS sends a "Device Provisioning Response" message back to the AIoT device vendor. This message contains an identity of the AIPS (AIPS Id) and a Token, which can be a randomly generated value associated with this ambient IoT device. In one example, the AIPS Id is a Fully Qualified Domain Name (FQDN) of the AIPS, which can be resolved to an Internet Protocol (IP) address using the Domain Name Service (DNS). The purpose of the Token is discussed in subsequent steps below.

In step 2, once the AIoT device vendor receives the "Device Provisioning Response" message containing the Token and AIPS Id, they print a QR code which contains:

- a. the device identifier (DevID),
- b. the AIoT Provisioning Server Identifier (AIPS Id) of the AIPS which stores the information of the AIoT device, and
- c. the "Token" which was sent from AIPS and has been received by the AIoT device vendor,

and attach this QR code on the AIoT device itself. Note that the use of QR code to transfer device-related information is only one example of how this information can be presented. Other means can also be used for providing this information from the AIoT device vendor to the AIoT Operator, e.g., sending this information in a data file, or via email, etc.

In step 3, the AIoT operator (aka "Vertical") buys the AIoT device and, after scanning the QR code, which is present on the AIoT device, deploys the device at a certain location.

In step 4, the AIoT AS sends a "Device Claim Request" message to the Network Exposure Function (NEF) of the 5G network. This message is sent after the AIoT Operator provides to the AIoT AS the device information obtained from the QR code. The "Device Claim Request" message contains AIoT device information including the DevID (Step 1a), the AIPS Id (Step 1b), the Token (Step 1b), the Location where the AIoT device has been deployed and an identifier of the AIoT Application Server (AIoT AS Id) used by the AIoT operator. In

Fig. 1. AIoT Onboarding procedure

other scenarios, the “Device Claim Request” message can contain information, not only for a single AIoT device, but for a plurality (or a group) of AIoT devices. The NEF authenticates the “Device Claim Request” message (with existing means which are outside the scope of this paper) and then relays this message to an AIoTF in the 5G core network. If there are multiple AIoTFs deployed in the 5G core network, the NEF selects one of them by using the information available in step 4. (For example, the AIoTF may be selected by using one or more of the following parameters in message #4: AIPS Id, Location, AIoT AS Id.)

In step 5a, the AIoT Function (AIoTF) in the 5G network initiates the AIoT device onboarding procedure by sending a “Device Onboarding Request” message to the AIPS. The contact information (e.g., the IP address) of the AIPS can be derived from the AIPS Id, received in step 4. The “Device Onboarding Request” message contains the DevID and the Token received in step 4, as well as the identity of the 5G network, referred to as the “Home Network Id”. The Token information in step 5a can be the same as the Token received in step 4 or another value derived (e.g., using a hash function) from the Token in step 4. In the latter case, the Token is presented as Token*.

In step 5b, the AIPS, upon receiving the “Device Onboarding Request” message by the AIoTF, validates the received Token (or Token*), i.e., it determines whether it matches the Token value securely stored in the AIPS for this device. If Token validation is successful, AIPS stores the received Home Network Id and proceeds to step 5c; otherwise, the received request is rejected.

In step 5c, the AIPS sends a “Device Onboarding Response” message back to the AIoTF of the 5G network, which contains the device information that is securely stored in

the AIPS. The “Device Onboarding Response” message contains the “Security Info” and the “Dev profile” of the AIoT device (this information has been made available to the AIPS in Step 1a).

In step 6, the AIoTF, upon receiving a successful “Device Onboarding Response” message from AIPS, creates and stores an *AIoT Device Context* for the relevant AIoT device. This *AIoT Device Context* contains various information for the AIoT device including the DevID, the Token, the Security Info, the Dev profile, the Location of the AIoT device, the AIoT AS Id, etc.

In step 7, the AIoTF of the 5G network, sends (through NEF) a “Device Claim Response” message back to the AIoT AS. The “Device Claim Response” message encapsulates a “Success” or “Failure” indication that denotes the outcome of the device claiming procedure. Note that with this device claiming procedure (steps 4-7) the AIoT AS claims ownership of the AIoT device and instructs the 5G network to forward all subsequent messages from this AIoT device toward the AIoT AS. From this point onwards, once the “Device Claim Response” message (received by the AIoT AS in step 7) encapsulates a “Success” indication, the AIoT device can exchange information with the AIoT AS, as described below.

In step 10, the AIoT device harvests energy e.g., from the RF transmissions of one or more 5G Base Stations (gNBs) or from other sources.

In step 11, the AIoT device, having harvested enough energy to operate, transmits an uplink message which is received by a gNB (or multiple gNBs) and is forwarded to the AIoTF. This uplink message encapsulates the DevID, a “Payload” and a “Message Authentication Code” (MAC). The MAC has been created using the security information stored in the AIoT device (see step 0) and the “Payload”. For example,

the MAC can be derived as HashFunctionType(security key, “Payload”), where the HashFunctionType and the security key are part of the security information stored in the AIoT device and in the AIoTF (received in step 5c).

In step 12, the AIoTF receives the uplink message transmitted by the AIoT device (via one or more gNBs) and validates the MAC value in this message, i.e., it derives its own MAC value using the device information stored in the AIoTF (e.g., again using HashFunctionType(security key, “Payload”)) and examines whether the MAC value created by AIoTF matches the received MAC from the AIoT device. If they match, the received uplink message is deemed authentic and AIoTF proceeds to the next step; otherwise, AIoTF discards the received uplink message.

In step 13, the AIoTF sends (via NEF) an “AIoT Data” message to the AIoT AS. The identity of the AIoT AS is retrieved from the stored AIoT device context. The “AIoT Data” message encapsulates the DevID and the Payload of the message transmitted by the AIoT device. Note that the Payload may be encrypted and only the AIoT AS can decrypt this message using App-layer security information. This security information is not provided to the 5G network, i.e., it is different from the security information provided by AIPS in step 5c. Hence, the 5G network cannot interpret the app-layer information exchanged between the AIoT device and its associated AIoT AS. However, the 5G network can validate the authenticity of the received uplink messages, as explained above.

IV. SUPPORTING TX REQUIREMENTS

This section describes an extension of the steps analyzed in Section III, in an attempt to support Tx Requirements, which is essentially a parameter that enables the AIoT operator to specify a desired message transmission rate for an AIoT device or for a group of AIoT devices. The proposed steps illustrated in Fig. 2, are described below wherein we emphasize on the differences to the steps of the onboarding procedure.

Steps 0-3, remain the same as steps 0-3 of Section III.

Step 4 includes also transmission requirements (Tx Requirements) indicating the number of messages that the AIoT device should preferably transmit in a given time period.

Steps 5a-5c, remain the same as steps 5a-5c of Section III.

In step 6, the “Device Context” which is created and stored by AIoTF in this step, includes also the “Tx Requirements” parameter (indicated by the AIoT AS in Step 4).

Step 7 remains the same as step 7 of Section III.

In step 10, the AIoTF determines AIoT energy parameters for the gNB serving the location of the AIoT device. The AIoT energy parameters are derived based on the Tx Requirements of the considered AIoT device, but also based on the Tx Requirements of all other AIoT devices served by the same AIoT-capable gNB. Essentially, the AIoT energy parameters indicate to a gNB how to modify its RF transmissions and provide more or less energy that can be harvested by nearby AIoT devices. As an example, the AIoT energy parameters may indicate to gNB to increase or decrease the power or the rate of its RF transmissions, which supply energy to nearby AIoT devices. Note that, since the AIoTF cannot know how much RF energy the AIoT device can harvest (because it cannot know the exact amount of RF energy reaching the device), the AIoTF can only provide a rough estimation of the AIoT energy parameters for the considered gNB. After observing the number of transmissions performed by the AIoT device (and all other AIoT devices in the vicinity of the gNB), it can adjust the provided AIoT energy parameters accordingly.

In step 11, the AIoTF sends an “AIoT energy configuration” message to the AIoT-capable gNB serving the AIoT device. This message carries the AIoT energy parameters determined in step 10. In other words, the “AIoT energy configuration” message contains energy configuration instructions, which indicate to gNB how to alter the amount of transmitted RF energy that is harvested by nearby AIoT devices, in order to fulfil the requested Tx Requirements of the AIoT device.

Fig. 2. Supporting Tx Requirements

In step 12, the gNB which has received the “AIoT energy configuration” message, transmits an amount of “RF Energy for AIoT devices” that is adjusted according to the AIoT energy parameters received in step 11. The “RF Energy for AIoT devices” is an RF signal (or a combination of RF signals) at a specific frequency band which is harvested by the AIoT devices in the vicinity of the gNB.

In step 15, the AIoT device harvests energy from the RF signal emitted by the gNB. Every time the AIoT device harvests enough energy, it wakes up and may perform a transmission of an uplink message, which contains a Payload that is forwarded to an AIoT AS, as illustrated in Section III, steps 11-13.

In step 16, the AIoTF determines again new AIoT energy parameters for the gNB by observing the number of transmissions performed by the AIoT devices in the vicinity of the gNB and by comparing this number with the preferred number of transmissions of each AIoT device. For example, if the AIoTF determines that some AIoT devices fail to satisfy their Tx Requirements, the AIoTF will derive new AIoT energy parameter that will cause the gNB to increase the transmitted “RF Energy for AIoT devices”, i.e., increase the power of the transmitted RF signal, or the rate of RF energy emissions, or even both.

In step 17, the AIoTF sends an updated “AIoT energy configuration” message to the AIoT-capable gNB (as in step 11) to provide the new AIoT energy parameters determined in previous step.

The flow described in steps 11 through 17 is repeated periodically targeting to fulfil the AIoT device-preferable Tx Requirements set by the AIoT Operator (in step 4). However, it cannot be guaranteed that the Tx Requirements of an AIoT device will be met because the AIoT device may never be able to harvest enough RF energy due to detrimental communication conditions.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

Ambient IoT devices, with their distinct inherent characteristics, entail very specific communication requirements which demand for further enhancements in the 5G network architecture. The work presented in this paper is twofold; it initially targets to build upon the existing physical layer techniques and identify the necessary 3GPP-conforming network functions and message flows required to onboard AIoT devices onto 5G networks and enable their efficient end-to-end communication. In addition, it proposes novel methods which allow 5G networks to receive AIoT transmission requirements from AIoT application servers, and translate them into appropriate actions in the NG-RAN so as to energize the selected AIoT devices accordingly.

This paper shares the vision on 5G-and-beyond network adaptations, aiming to assist in the common 3GPP standardization efforts around ambient IoT communications which have just commenced. The novel elements and procedures described throughout this paper, include the introduction of the AIoT Provisioning Server (AIPS) which stores the AIoT device manufacturing information and validates the authenticity of an AIoT device, the AIoT Function (AIoTF) which is proposed as a new NF in the 5G

CN architecture and is expected to handle all the AIoT related procedures into the network, the onboarding procedure of an AIoT device into AIPS via the 5G network, and finally, the 5G network specific procedures allowing the translation of Tx Requirements (set by the AIoT Operator) into appropriate network decisions in terms of energy emission through RF signals by the gNBs.

Our future research activities in this topic, include the development of an experimentation testbed based on the proposed architecture and validation of the suggested methods. Another research aspect to consider is a slight variation in the proposed AIoT onboarding procedure, with the inclusion of an Ambient IoT Blockchain Network (AIBN) instead of the Ambient IoT Provisioning Server (AIPS). Similar to AIPS, the AIBN could store the AIoT device manufacturing information provided by the “AIoT Device Vendor”, as a record in the blockchain's distributed ledger. With its immutable records, the AIBN introduces an additional level of security and transparency, further ensuring that the AIoT device records in the distributed ledger cannot be altered or tampered in a fraudulent way, and that in such cases the event will be recorded in the form of a transaction, transparent to all blockchain network members. The blockchain perspective in enabling efficient and secure end-to-end AIoT communication is an open research area we also intend to investigate as part of our future directions.

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